

Studies on the Reactivity of Oxomolybdenum(v) Species in Solution and Solid State and in different Anionic Environment in Presence of 2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzthiazole

S. S. MANDAL*, P. C. GHORAI, T. K. RAY CHAUDHURI and H. K. SAHA

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, University of Calcutta, 92 Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 25 August 1992, revised 5 November 1992, accepted 19 January 1993

The paper deals with the study of the reactions of oxomolybdenum(v) species under different anionic environments like Cl^- and ox^{2-} ions both in solid state as well as in solutions in presence of 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole (PBT) leading to the synthesis of various paramagnetic derivatives PBTH_2 [MoOCl_5], [MoOCl_3PBT], [$\text{MoOCl}(\text{ox})\text{PBT}$] and diamagnetic or feebly paramagnetic derivatives [$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4(\text{PBT})_2$], [$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{PBT})_2$] and $(\text{PBTH}_2)_2[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4(\text{ox})_2]$. The composition of the compounds has been established through elemental analysis and various physicochemical studies, like uv-visible, ir and epr spectral analysis.

Oxo-metal ions of transitional elements can display interesting chemical characteristics which are largely dependent on the strength of metal-oxygen bonding energy and other important experimental conditions. Molybdenum is unique in forming very stable oxospecies MoO^{3+} cation with d^1 -configuration in its quinquivalent state and it exhibits very interesting chemical characteristics under diverse anionic environment like Cl^- , Br^- , ox^{2-} , H_2PO_4^- etc., which have been extensively studied by Saha and his coworkers^{1,2}. Due to the positional advantage of double bonded oxygen (triple bond character) in MoO^{3+} moiety which may be due to $p\pi-d\pi$ bonding in octahedral geometry of the complexes, the 'acidic group' *trans* to this oxygen of MoO^{3+} ion in aqueous medium gives an additional advantage of its elimination with the subsequent formation of oxo-bridge leading to the substantial reduction in paramagnetism. This reduction in paramagnetism depends obviously on the frequency of

vibration of $(-\text{Mo}^{\text{X}}\text{Mo}-)$ unit which is again dependent on the Van der Waals radius of 'X' and the other ligands attached to the metals (mono- or bidentate; neutral or acidic; partly neutral or partly acidic).

For this reason, the present authors have taken up a detailed scheme of investigation on the effect of different nitrogen based organic compounds including amino acids and vitamins to study the change in behaviour of the oxomolybdenum(v) species under different conditions like (i) diverse anionic environment,

(ii) in solution (aqueous and non-aqueous media) and (iii) in solid state and under different acidity and temperature. The present communication deals with the synthesis and its characterisation of some molybdenum(v) compounds using 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole (PBT) as metal-binding substance which contains interesting donor species ($\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{N}-$) similar to 2,2'-bipyridyl and 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole.

Results and Discussion

The salt $(\text{PBTH}_2)[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ is a crystalline green solid and is stable at room temperature. The green colour gradually changes to greenish yellow on long standing in the desiccator and ultimately becomes insoluble in water. This is probably due to partial elimination of hydrogen chloride from the molecule, strong binding property of the ligand and the affinity for MoO^{3+} forming the non-electrolytic compound,

Dehydrohalogenation reaction was carried out by refluxing the parent salt with different solvents, like absolute alcohol, acetonitrile and acetylacetone yielding the non-electrolytic compounds with the same chemical composition [MoOCl_3PBT], but difference in colours violet and red. The difference in colours is probably due to stereoisomers *cis* and *trans* varieties. The violet variety which reacts with water and is acidic to litmus may be the *cis*-form and the red variety which

is neutral to litmus may be the *trans*-variety. As the compounds are insoluble in non-polar solvents, their dipole moment measurements were not possible. The parent salt undergoes substitution with oxalic acid in solid state in inert atmosphere yielding the non-electrolyte [MoOCl(ox)PBT]. However, this reaction on performing in aqueous media, a salt type compound results (PBTH₂)₂ [Mo₂O₃Cl₄(ox)₂].

The molar conductance value for the salt (1119 Ω⁻¹ cm²) is compatible with 1 : 1 electrolyte³. For the non-electrolytes the values range from 5.77 to 33.99 Ω⁻¹ cm² (Table 1) which are much less than the binary electrolytes. As the compound (PBTH₂)₂[Mo₂O₃Cl₄(ox)₂] is found to be highly sensitive towards moisture and air, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility values with reasonable accuracy were not available. The values for the oxalate derivatives were found to be somewhat high, which is definitely due to ionisation in solution.

The room temperature magnetic susceptibilities

cases of monooxo- and dioxo-species⁴. From epr spectra, the average <g> values were calculated, which also support *d*¹-configuration of the oxo-metal ion. The epr spectrum of PBTH₂ [MoOCl₅] is given in Fig. 1. The ν_{Mo-O} band of this compound appears at 950 cm⁻¹ in the corresponding ir spectrum.

The ir spectra of the complexes exhibit a very strong absorption at 930–980 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned as the vibration of the symmetric stretching mode of the terminal Mo=O band⁵. The bands at 750–770 cm⁻¹ are assignable to ν_{Mo-O-Mo} vibration⁶. The band near 1600 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to ν_{C=N} + ν_{O=C} vibration. In the complexes however, this band has been reduced considerably by about 20–40 cm⁻¹, indicating the coordination through the pyridyl and benzthiazole nitrogens. The pyridine ring breathing mode of the free ligand (990 cm⁻¹) which is raised to higher frequencies by 15–20 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, suggests coordination of pyridine nitrogen to the metal ion^{7,8}. The bands in the uv and visible regions

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Oxidation state of Mo	Molar conductance Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	ν _{Mo-O} ν _{Mo-O-Mo} cm ⁻¹	μ _{eff} * B.M.	<g>
		Mo	N	Cl	ox					
1.	PBTH ₂ [MoOCl ₅]	19.44 (19.05)	5.91 (5.36)	35.81 (35.23)	—	4.89	111.99	980	1.60 (301)	1.84
2.	[MoOCl ₅ .PBT], (violet)	22.46 (22.28)	6.73 (6.50)	25.10 (24.74)	—	4.92	11.20	960	1.74 (299)	1.82
	[MoOCl ₅ .PBT], (red)	22.01 (22.28)	6.80 (6.50)	25.05 (24.74)	—	5.00	5.77	970	1.80 (299)	1.83
	[MoOCl ₅ .PBT], (red)	22.51 (22.28)	6.51 (6.50)	24.97 (24.74)	—	4.97	12.88	960	1.74 (299)	1.82
3.	[MoCl(ox)PBT]	21.52 (21.44)	5.87 (6.25)	8.19 (7.93)	20.45 (19.66)	5.10	33.99	970	1.56 (301)	1.83
4.	[Mo ₂ O ₃ Cl ₄ (PBT) ₂]	24.27 (23.80)	7.41 (6.94)	17.91 (17.62)	—	5.00	7.05	975, 770	1.19 (299)	—
5.	[Mo ₂ O ₃ Cl ₂ (PBT) ₂]	26.12 (25.55)	8.02 (7.45)	10.16 (9.45)	—	5.09	7.32	930, 750	Diamag.	—
6.	(PBTH ₂) ₂ [Mo ₂ O ₃ Cl ₄ (ox) ₂]	20.15 (19.46)	4.99 (5.68)	15.11 (14.40)	17.33 (17.85)	5.05	—	940, 770	—	—

* Room temperature (K) is given in parenthesis.

of the salt and its monooxo-derivatives were found to be in the range 1.56–1.80 B.M., which confirms the presence of MoO³⁺ (Table 1) unit in these compounds with *d*¹-configuration of molybdenum. Diamagnetic behaviour of [Mo₂O₃Cl₂(PBT)₂] is expected due to the presence of Mo₂O₄²⁺ moiety. However, reduced paramagnetism has been observed as is expected in the

are fairly in good agreement with those of the similar compounds having octahedral geometry^{9,10}.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by a modified method of Rao and Wahlgren¹¹, wherein the condensation of

Fig 1 EPR spectrum of 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazolium oxo-pentachloro-molybdate(v) in solid state

pyridine-2-carboxylic acid with *o*-aminothiophenol was performed more conveniently in hot orthophosphoric acid medium. In the exothermic reaction initiated at $\sim 180^\circ$ and at $\sim 200^\circ$ profuse evolution of water vapour occurred.

Molybdenum and chloride were estimated gravimetrically as oxinate¹² and as silver chloride. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas method. Oxalate was estimated volumetrically after separating Mo^V as hydroxide. The oxidation state was determined by ceric sulphate method. The conductivity was measured in acetonitrile using a Dip type cell. The magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature. The $\langle g \rangle$ values were measured by a E-112 epr spectrometer. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (acetonitrile) on a Perkin-Elmer 550S spectrophotometer.

2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzthiazolium oxopentachloromolybdate(v), $\text{PBTH}_2 [\text{MoOCl}_5]$: Molybdenum trioxide (1 g) was reduced by HI (1 ml) in 12 *M*HCl medium¹. To the bright green resulting solution, the ligand (1.5 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of 12

M HCl was added in ice-cold condition. A green crystalline compound separated out from the solution on standing. The product was washed with portions of concentrated HCl and dried in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH, (~ 1.7 g).

Oxotrichloro[2-2'-pyridylbenzthiazole]molybdenum(v), $[\text{MoOCl}_3, \text{PBT}]$. (a) *Violet variety* : The parent salt $\text{PBTH}_2 [\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (1 g) was refluxed with absolute ethanol (15 ml) for 1 h, when dehydrohalogenation took place and a violet coloured compound was formed. The product was dried under reduced pressure, (0.72 g).

(b) *Red variety* : The compounds with identical composition of red variety were prepared by refluxing the parent salt (1 g) in acetonitrile (20 ml) and acetylacetone (20 ml) respectively. In the former case yield was 0.75 g and in the later ~ 0.6 g.

Oxochloro-oxalato-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole molybdenum(v), $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{ox})\text{PBT}]$: The salt $\text{PBTH}_2 [\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (1.25 g) and oxalic acid (0.32 g) were powdered separately and then mixed thoroughly. The mixture was then heated on a porcelain boat at 130° in a current of dry CO_2 until the evolution of HCl gas ceased. The green coloured residue so formed was washed with minimum quantity of acetonitrile and dried under reduced pressure, (~ 0.85 g).

Oxo- μ -oxo-trichlorobis-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole molybdenum(v). $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4(\text{PBT})_2]$: The salt $\text{PBTH}_2 [\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (~ 1 g) was refluxed with ethanol and water mixture (1 : 1) for 1 h. The brick-red coloured compound obtained on cooling, was washed with water-ethanol mixture and dried under reduced pressure, (0.66 g).

Oxo- μ -dioxodichlorobis-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole molybdenum(v). $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_2(\text{PBT})_2]$: The salt $\text{PBTH}_2 [\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (1 g) was refluxed with distilled water (20 ml) for 1 h. The red coloured compound separated out on cooling the mixture to room temperature, was dried under reduced pressure, (0.65 g).

Bis-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazoliumoxo- μ -oxotetrachlorobisoxalatomolybdate(v), $(\text{PBTH}_2)_2 [\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4(\text{ox})_2]$: The salt $\text{PBTH}_2 [\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (~ 1 g) was added to a saturated solution (15 ml) of oxalic acid containing oxalic acid (2.5 g) and the mixture was stirred well and warmed slightly. The resulting pale yellow coloured solid was washed with water-ethanol

mixture (1 : 1) and dried under reduced pressure, (0.65 g).

The analytical and physical data are given in Table 1.

References

1. H. K. SAHU and M. C. HALDER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 3719.
2. H. K. SAHU and A. K. BANERJEE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 607.
3. W. J. GIBSON, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
4. M. C. BAIRD, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **9**, 29.
5. K. FENAN and G. W. A. FOWLIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 310.
6. W. E. NEWTON and J. W. McDONALD, 'Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on the Chemistry and Uses of Molybdenum', 1977, p. 29.
7. S. P. GHOSH and L. K. MISHRA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **7**, 545.
8. S. J. GRUBAR, C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1805.
9. H. G. GRAY and C. R. HARR, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 363.
10. P. C. H. MITCHELL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 965.
11. J. T. N. RAO and C. G. WAHLGREN, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1983, **20**, 1481.
12. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., ELBS, London, 1972, p. 580.